

November 2025

Kingston Homeless Alliance

Overview of Homelessness in Kingston, Ontario - A Literature Review

Photo taken by Crosby Rosenthal

“Created by youth. Informed by the community.”

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1. Background:

Kingston, Ontario monitors homelessness using a “By-Name List” (BNL) and participates in the national Point-in-Time (PiT) Count under the federal Reaching Home initiative (Homelessness learning hub, 2024). Throughout 2024, the BNL tracked an average of about 560 individuals, ending the year with 521 people, 63% of whom met the definition of chronic homelessness (Figure 2) (City of Kingston, 2024). In total, over 2,200 unique clients accessed homelessness-related supports such as outreach, shelter, and housing programs. These figures highlight a persistent level of housing instability in the city, similar to national patterns where around 60,000 people were counted as homeless across Canada in 2024 (City of Kingston, 2024).

2. Methods:

A comprehensive search of the literature was performed using the Google Scholar, PubMed, and Homelessness Learning Hub databases on September 20th 2025. Eligibility criteria included peer-reviewed journal articles, municipal and federal government reports, and community-based publications focusing on homelessness in Kingston, Ontario. Opinion pieces, non-Canadian studies, and sources lacking primary data or official reporting were excluded. All studies were independently screened by two reviewers (M.T. and P.C.) to ensure relevance and data accuracy, with any conflicts resolved by a third reviewer (L.P.). The primary outcomes examined included the prevalence and demographics of homelessness, barriers to stable housing, health and mental health outcomes, and municipal responses such as shelter initiatives and encampment management strategies.

3. Results and Discussion:

3.1 Current living situations (November 2024 PiT):

Of the 288 people surveyed in Kingston's 2024 PiT count, 37% were staying in emergency or domestic-violence shelters, 28% in transitional housing, 27% were unsheltered, 2% had no fixed address, and 6% experienced hidden homelessness (Figure 1) (United Way of Kingston, 2024). The remaining individuals reported other temporary living arrangements. The PiT Count is designed as a 24-hour minimum snapshot, which means it captures only a single day's circumstances and likely underrepresents the full extent of homelessness (Homelessness learning hub, 2024). Especially among people who are temporarily sheltered or “hidden” within informal housing situations.

3.2 Demographics and Over-representation:

Kingston's 2024 PiT Count reveals significant overrepresentation of Indigenous people compared to the city's general population. 23% of respondents identified as First Nations, 5.5% as Métis, and 0.5% as Inuit. Most participants identified as White while 5% identified as Black and smaller proportions from other racialized groups (United Way of Kingston, 2024). Other

findings from the 2024 Pit Count further highlight the diverse yet vulnerable populations affected by homelessness in Kingston. A small proportion of people identified as veterans (2%), immigrants (3%), or refugees and asylum claimants (1%) (United Way of Kingston, 2024). Educational attainment was also low with only 30% completing high school and 23% post-secondary studies (Canada, 2024). Additionally, 26% of respondents had a history in foster care showing how early-life instability and systemic inequities contribute to the cycles of homelessness (City of Kingston, 2022).

3.3 Key Barriers to Transitioning out of Homelessness:

When survey participants were questioned about what they felt was preventing them from obtaining permanent housing in Kingston, an overwhelming number cited problems relating to income and rent. 96% of respondents reported that they did not have a high enough income to afford rent. 84% stated that rent was too high in Kingston to be considered as affordable (City of Kingston, 2024). Additionally, 23% reported that housing options were not suitable. Furthermore, 4% indicated that housing was unavailable (CFI Team, 2023). A sustainable source of income is a struggle for many facing homelessness in Kingston. 82% of survey respondents reported a dependency on government programs such as Disability Benefit and Welfare/Social Assistance. Only 7% reported an income through formal employment of any kind (Community Homelessness Report, 2024). Pending housing related issues, the most common barriers that were reported were 42% acknowledging discrimination, 35% reporting mental health issues, 29% facing the breakdown of a relationship/family connection, and 28% admitting to substance use/addiction (City of Kingston, 2024).

3.4 Health, Mental Health, and Substance Use:

Multiple Kingston surveys and service reports confirm that mental health and substance use challenges are pervasive among those experiencing homelessness. About 75% reported mental-health issues and 67% reported substance-use challenges, both significantly higher than in prior years (City of Kingston, 2024). Among youth, these rates were even higher with 88% experiencing mental-health difficulties and 79% reporting substance-use problems (Community Homelessness Report, 2024). Public-health data from Kingston's Consumption and Treatment Services also showed a 15% weekly rise in drug poisoning in early 2024 (KFL&A Public Health, 2024). These findings suggest a strong link between housing instability, mental health, and substance use. This emphasizes the need for coordinated and trauma-informed health and housing supports (Lezhanska Anastasiya et al., 2024).

3.5 Encampments & System Response:

Encampments are defined as temporary, outdoor campsites, typically with two or more tents/structures. In 2024, more people were unsheltered sleeping in rough conditions or encampments (27%) than in 2021 (8%). This comes as the total number of homelessness dramatically increased by 133% (Community Homelessness Report, 2024). Addressing

encampments has been a difficult situation for the city of Kingston. A ‘open’ letter from the Ontario Human Rights Commission to the City of Kingston emphasized that “municipalities are not adopting a consistent response to this growing concern” (City of Kingston, 2022). In 2022, the City of Kingston resolved to create an Encampment Response Pilot Project, to suspend current plans for any evictions until an alternative can be created to find a more permanent and safer housing situation (City of Kingston, 2022). Despite an increase in shelter capacity, occupancy percentage has barely increased from 75% in 2021 to 77% in 2024 (City of Kingston, 2024). The reason for this is believed to be influenced by but not limited to safety concerns, crowding in the shelters, and certain service restrictions.

3.6 What the Kingston Health System is Seeing:

In early 2024, Kingston Public Health authority reported an alert related to the rise in drug-related poisonings. The increase in poisonings from the previous week was 15%, which resulted in the alert (KFL&A Public Health, 2024). A correlation between opioid-related toxicity deaths in Ontario shelters and mental health related healthcare encounters seems to exist. 94% of shelter deaths had a mental health-related healthcare encounter in the prior 5 years and 79% had a hospital based encounter for a mental health diagnosis (Lezhanska Anastasiya et al., 2024). Healthcare program initiatives have helped provide some healthcare to homeless individuals. These include Kingston Community Health Centres and the Street Health location, which help facilitate health-associated outreach services. From the PiT survey, 32% of participants reported a visitation to a hospital or health-related facility in 2024 (Community Homelessness Report, 2024). This low percentage can be explained by a stigma facing vulnerable housed individuals when it comes to engaging with health care providers. Many feel judgement or disrespect from health care providers, especially with regards to assumptions about substance abuse. This makes them feel alienated, ignored because of predisposed judgment, which discourages these individuals from seeking help.

4. Conclusion:

Kingston’s evidence shows persistent, system level homelessness: high By Name List counts, a PiT snapshot with more people unsheltered, and marked overrepresentation of Indigenous peoples. Barriers cluster around affordability, with insufficient incomes, high rents, and limited suitable units. These pressures intersect with discrimination, trauma, mental health needs, and substance use. Health system touchpoints and rising drug abuse and overdose point to the need for coordinated, trauma informed, culturally safe care. Future directions should expand supportive and deeply affordable housing, rent supplements, and income adequacy. Prioritize Indigenous led solutions and low barrier harm reduction that is integrated with primary and mental health care. Pair the By Name List with longitudinal follow up beyond the PiT snapshot, improve data sharing across systems, and evaluate encampment responses using resident defined safety and choice while centering lived experience in design and evaluation.

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Figure 1: Where people were staying during Kingston’s 2024 PiT Count (United Way of Kingston, 2024).

Figure 2: People who experienced homelessness for at least one day in the month, Kingston (March 2020–March 2028) with a target line (Community Homelessness Report, 2024)

